

FROM LEXICAL FIELDS TO CONCEPTUAL NETWORKS: A COGNITIVE APPROACH TO VOCABULARY ORGANIZATION

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Abstract:

This article explores the perspectives of the cognitive approach to the semantic field and theory, and hypothesizes that semantic fields are not merely structural groupings of lexemes within the vocabulary system but represent cognitively structured conceptual domains in the mental lexicon. From the perspective of Cognitive Linguistics, the organization of lexical units within semantic fields reflects conceptual categorization, prototype effects, and associative conceptual networks that structure human knowledge and linguistic meaning. Drawing on cognitive linguistics, conceptual metaphor theory, and frame semantics, this study explores how understanding of meaning relates to general cognitive processes.

Key words:

Semantic field, cognitive linguistics, frame semantics, conceptual metaphor.

Introduction

In modern linguistics, the study of semantic fields is crucial because it reflects a broader vision than viewing language as a set of lexical units used for communicative purposes. Linguistics is an interdisciplinary science connected with philosophy, psychology, literature, sociology, culture and so on. The linguistic subject which studies meaning as part of the human cognition is called cognitive semantics, now a rapidly developing branch of linguistics. It was Michele Breal who introduced the term 'semantics' to designate a linguistic discipline which studies the content of the language units and the speech expressions which are made of these units. [Breal, 1897]. After him Ferdinand de Saussure developed the idea of structural semantics, with an emphasis on the language as a system of signs [Saussure, 1916]. The present study employs a theoretical and analytical methodology combining approaches from lexical semantics, structural semantics, and Cognitive Linguistics. The methodological framework is designed to investigate how semantic fields can be interpreted not only as lexical systems but also as conceptual structures in the mental lexicon.

Main body

Semantics is a branch of linguistics which studies meaning in language. It explores how words and phrases convey meaning, how meaning is structured, and how they relate to human thinking. It studies the meaning of lexical units both in the language system and in speech acts [Tukhtakhodjaeva Z.T., 2021: 20-25].

M.Breal's approach to semantic analysis was mainly diachronic which focused on semantic change and processes reflecting how word meanings evolve over time. [Breal, 1897]. His ideas were later developed by a famous structuralist Ferdinand de Saussure, who at the beginning of XX century introduced the concept of linguistic signs, which consist of *signifier* (sound/image of the world) and *signified* (concept/meaning). He argued that the relationship between signified and signifier is arbitrary because it depends on mental concept. Saussure claimed that meaning exists not independently, but through differences between linguistic units or thought. [Saussure, 1916]. Inspired by Ferdinand de Saussure, Trier introduced semantic field theory, which is group of words that are related in meaning and belong to the

same fields. He argued that vocabulary forms structured systems and meaning exists through relationship within a field, when word changes, semantic fields also restructured. [Trier, 1931] Trier's approach was diachronic, because he studied how semantic fields change over time, how they come to include a new word or exclude old ones.

Following him, Steven Ullmann may be said to have "opened a new phrase in the history or semantics" [Ullmann, 1977: 54]. A semantic field made up of a list of incompatible words relating to objects of a specific class is demonstrated using Trier's field theory. We can make deduction based on this theory:

Under a common concept, some words could constitute a semantic field. For instance, the terms "cat," "dog," "horse," "tiger," "elephant," and so on can all be considered members of a semantic field under the classifier "animal" Lyons emphasizes the systemic organization of vocabulary and semantic relations between words. He strongly noted that "the vocabulary of a language is structured in terms of a network of sense-relations" [Lyons, 1977:270]. This idea supports the view that lexical items are organized into **structured semantic systems**, which correspond to semantic fields [Lyons, 1995:117].

This research is based on a critical analysis of classical semantic field theory developed in structural linguistics, particularly in the works of Jost Trier and later studies in lexical semantics by Stephen Ullmann. Ullmann developed semantic field ideas further and stressed that "words are not isolated units but form part of a network of associations based on similarity, contrast and contiguity." [Ullmann, 1962:57] He emphasized that vocabulary is organized into interconnected semantic systems, reflecting relationships between lexical meanings. [Ullman 1977;167].

Their models describe vocabulary as a structured system of lexical units organized into semantic fields defined by paradigmatic relations. Later George Lakoff and Charles Fillmore further developed the branches. Cognitive linguistics represents a shift in how we think about the world. Instead of thinking about abstract set of rules, language is deeply rooted in our human experience and the way we observe, compare, categorize, conceptualize, nominalize.

According to George Lakoff, the conceptual metaphor isn't just a poetic device, it is a cognitive mechanism of human thought. We understand abstract concepts, like *time* and *argument* by mapping them into other things. For example, *Argument is war* this sentence always used to describe *argument* like "defending a position" or "attacking a weak point". By this point, Lakoff argues that, we do not speak in metaphors, we think in them, and we create new things and we compare things with these metaphors [Lakoff, 1980].

Fillmore provides us with information about frame semantics, which are scenes, while Lakoff is concerned with mapping abstract objects. He developed the basics of frame semantics, which suggest that we cannot understand the meaning of a single word without understanding the entire conceptual structure surrounding it. For example, the concept of "commercial exchange" frame. Fillmore argues that, to understand the word *buy*, we should know the concepts of *a seller*, *a buyer*, *goods*, and *money* as they are all part of "commercial exchange" frame [Fillmore, 2003]

Conclusion

The central theoretical argument of the paper is the idea that semantic fields can be interpreted not only as lexical systems, but also as conceptual networks in the mental lexicon. Their conceptual characteristics can be presented as prototype structures with central vs

peripheral members, associative conceptual links and conceptual domains. For example, the semantic field HEALTH may include core concepts such as health, illness, disease, treatment, and peripheral concepts, such as therapy, recovery, prevention, diagnosis, etc. These relations form a conceptual network rather than a fixed lexical hierarchy. In conclusion, semantics provides essential device for analyzing language as both a cognitive system and communicative tool. Meaning is dynamic, context dependent, and deeply rooted in human experience. Therefore, the study of semantics remains fundamental for understanding language structures.

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